

WHY FINANCIAL SECTORS MUST STRENGTHEN CYBERSECURITY

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Abstract— This study article mainly aims to identify why we need financial cybersecurity. The study also aims to show the significant influence and advantages of cyber safety in banking systems in a business. In addition, this research aims to promote cybersecurity usage, guaranteeing safe information, and managing the risk of information efficiently [1]. However, many banking and finance firms are still cautious in terms of cybersecurity application and use. Indeed, the benefits of cybersecurity might not be known to these financial organizations.

Moreover, the higher expenditures of its request might lead to the refusal. Several questions have thus been put to determine in these banks the level of cybersecurity knowledge and abilities. Despite the measures necessary, data loss can lead to a client spending many restless nights. To prevent cybersecurity dangers that might make your clients susceptible, cybersecurity is therefore vital to banking.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, risk, security, eBank and financial sector assaults, cyber risks threats

I. INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

As technology is increasing, many organizations, large or small, are entirely dependent on the use of IT systems in their daily activities, which requires the organization to take effective information security strategies into account to ensure that the sensitive and valuable databases of the institution are not being stolen [2]. The global banking sector has seen substantial changes in procedures, transactions, and operations in recent years that have been impacted by technology and innovation. In systemic processes and innovation in information technology, however, there are particular concerns. Banks provide many digital services based on third-party platforms. They are therefore dependent on mechanisms outside their control. This raises awareness of technical risks and loopholes for hackers and criminals to infiltrate financial systems and steal important information and cash. The fast technological progress is confronting cyber threats and assaults. The study will offer a basis for future studies on the banks' danger, strategies, and protection plans and awareness that banks and customers are aware of cyber risks and security. The survey will also focus on cyber assaults to safeguard their customers; Cybersecurity is a procedure meant to prevent unwanted access

and destruction or assault in cyberspace of computers, servers, networks, and digital data. The protection of its financial data, intellectual assets, and reputation as a vital component of its business plan must be a matter for organizations. In their usage of the cybersecurity component, enterprises and governments aim to secure their private information and guarantee the availability and integrity of the information.

Significant numbers of nations strive to establish a comprehensive plan for ensuring information security in cyberspace, as information security is part of the national security of every country. Many nations understood that technological growth leads to the nation's and citizens' problems for security. They must fight for cyber-security, which relies on the techniques and legal methods of resisting unlawful use of data. Research has shown that in the previous year, over 50% of UK firms have been involved in cyber violations or assaults at the Cyber Security Center of the UK Government (2017). Despite this, the UK Government has pledged \$2.5 billion to defend the country from cyber assaults to assist prepare and make the UK the safest place to operate online. Institutions need to take the lead in securing digital data for consumers. They provide cyber programs knowledgeable, e-training, cyber-based basis, and free consultations.

However, the Kingdom of Bahrain expert has noticed that cybersecurity will shortly be carried out in the Kingdom; the country has already started the government's campaign to raise cybersecurity awareness to explain how cyber safety is necessary to prevent online risks or threats. However, the government has indicated that hiring this IT safety system and the training of its personnel to develop them with strong cybersecurity understanding may take about four years. Despite the prominence of the government in implementing this plan through its active engagement in regional conferences and public awareness, its execution requires all stakeholders, whether the government, private sector, or international, to work in concert and cooperate [3]. However, cybersecurity is a crucial idea that many companies implement due to unique technology in company management. Companies all around the world thus need to understand the importance of cybersecurity and its implementation. The protection of data and information from unlawful theft, since these events have risen extensively in recent years, is one of the significant aims of cybersecurity. Cybersecurity benefits include enhancing the company's work, improving customer happiness, reducing bureaucracy, and enhancing cash flow, safety and certainty. The negatives, at the same time, include fraud risk, legal risk, and technological risk. According to ISACA (2017), information security is often used

interchangeably in the words "cybersecurity" and "informational security," but in fact, cybersecurity is part of the security of information. In specifically, as an alternative term for information security and risk management, the term cybersecurity practice. Nevertheless, cybersecurity is an information technology safety element that concentrates mainly on protection against illegal access or destruction of computers, programs, and digital data and assets. Cybersecurity often means how intended institutions and individuals might be preserved and protected against assaults, incidents, and repercussions.

The cybersecurity study is critical today because governments, companies, and financial institutions use information technology to handle private information and sometimes move the data across networks to other systems. The data must thus be protected. Each Business should have an initial cybersecurity risk identifying procedure which may be identified via classified information, measurement instruments, and so on risk measurement tools, risk communication, and threat identification. The company has to look at the capacity to safeguard and maintain systems and devices after identifying threats. However, new approaches to satisfy customer expectations are being matched with the growing dangers of cyber-attacks and new fraud practices. This study aims to illustrate the significant impact and the advantages of cyber safety application in the banking sector systems of the Business. The purpose of this study is also to encourage cybersecurity use to ensure safe and secure information Effective risk management of information. However, many organizations, as far as cybersecurity is concerned, remain cautious. Indeed, they may not be aware of the benefits of cybersecurity.

Furthermore, increasing expenses might be a factor for its refusal. Financial institutions have valuable customer information and large sums; this threatens the growth of technology capabilities in bank transactions and businesses [4]. These risks are known to criminals and hackers. They can employ technical procedures to target financial institutions' cybersecurity and steal information and money from customers in situations of violations. Cyber risks are seen as a significant problem in the banking sector, and thus banks should be kept informed about new technology trends in data protection. There is an absence of expertise, senior management support, and the professionalism of cybersecurity professionals in the sector.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In many respects, the financial industry stands for cybercrime; after all, it's money. Some of the assault types affecting financial organizations include fraud, theft of bank accounts, money washing, breaches of personal data, and terrorist funding. As a critical infrastructure for cyber thieves, the banking industry is a primary target. According to the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), this is confirmed by an 80 percent rise in cyber-attacks against financial institutions. In the 2017 study Accenture and the Ponemon Institute's Cost of Cyber Crime Study, financial services reported higher cybercrime expenditures than any other industry. The financial losses from

fraud in the UK amounted during the first half of 2018 to £ 705.7 million. Equifax also received a £500,000 punishment in the UK before the GDPR became operational in 2018.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The survey strengthened our awareness of cybersafety and its relevance to financial institutions. These findings may be used as suggestions for improvement in the detection of cyber assaults for their workers. Moreover, these findings are essential for the development and effect on these financial institutions' understanding of cybersecurity. In addition, this report might support the banks, as it gives positive cybersecurity suggestions

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

Over recent decades, bodily data and buildings have been the main focus of a financial institution's security system. The constantly developing technology, by contrast, has played an important role today in changing the traditional business activities into highly creative and facilitating banking operations [5]. However, a high-tech organization might face other problems, many of them leading to infringements and efforts by hackers to damage valuable assets. Consequently, by adopting cybersecurity systems, financial institutions must be careful and attentive to these dangers to manage and regulate them.

The Status of Cybersecurity in Banking

BBA and PWC have said the worldwide expansion of cyber dangers, and therefore methods to overcome threats must be adopted. The cyber duties of the banks are shared across many departments and may cause problems in identifying and prioritizing risks and the methods needed to deal with attacks. In addition to this, financial infiltration is regarded as the most significant assault since the bank data may be robbed, modified, and deleted. By using hardware, software, and human weaknesses, hackers may control the financial network, which leads to disastrous results. The consequence of security assaults against the bank includes harm to the bank's reputation, affecting financial market stability, and affecting share prices. Summerfield submitted the critical influence of digital technology on the banking sector. In terms of technical and digital transactions and operations, financial institutions rely extensively on third parties. The banks have therefore improved their efficiency in terms of technology. Regardless of the good impacts of technology on the banking sector, technology's negatives, especially cyber crimes, have lately increased.

The world's top 50, Summerfield added, was attacked, resulting in losses of 1 billion dollars yearly. Cybersecurity may offer banks a competitive edge and thus enhance safety measures to secure their data and earn consumer confidence.

Cawley (2020) said the banking industry struggles to keep pace with solid technology innovation trends, particularly laws relating to banking system operations. The technology legacy

is a customer disadvantage and poses significant security issues for banks and their customers. For example, Cawley noted that two factors are authenticated to safeguard customers' bank accounts by implementing cyber-attack protection. Banks would transmit codes to the customer's mobiles before log-in; in this scenario, attackers would need to access the account information and financial transactions via the mobile and computer [6]. Regardless of the efficiency of the proceedings, some financial organizations do not use two-factor authentication to safeguard their clients' bank accounts and information. He detailed the scenario of a bank in Bangladesh that had faults within the bank's computer system. They have discovered malware in the client system; assailants utilize this software to circumvent risk measures and initiate a money transfer. Kuepper (2017) has suggested that customers have modest losses from cyberbanking assaults as they would respond rapidly by alerting the bank on missing cash. In America, if the customer has been alerted within 60 days after the transaction, the law compels the banks to repay the client for the theft of funds from their accounts without their permission. McGoogan (2017) stated in The Telegraph that financial cyber-attack fraud cost end-users more than \$ 10.5 billion in 2016 and grew by 122 percent compared to the preceding year. Over the same period, online transactions rose by 10%. Therefore, online creditors are under increased stress to put more and more intelligent identification measures to expedite genuine and proper lending and end fraud.

No	Common Cyber-Crime	No of Reported Cases	Remarks
1	Bank account fraud	2,356,000	25% of customers opened "Phishing" emails.
2	Non-investment fraud	1,280,000	A Ponzi scheme is a fake investing scam guaranteeing huge percentage of return with barely any risk to investors. The Ponzi scheme generates high returns for earlier investors by securing new investors and will eventually collapse as a result.
3	Computer virus	1,340,000	Unauthorized software such as Ransomware which asks for ransom to recover your system again.
4	Hacking	681,000	Hacking is unauthorized accessing to information systems resources. Hackers are criminals who abuse security weakness to illegally access to the network to steal sensitive information and send spam.
5	Advance fee fraud	117,000	The victim is ensured access to a significant share of a huge amount of money, in return for a small straightforward payment.
6	Other fraud	116,000	One of these examples is "Solicitor Scam" where the hackers hack a lawyer webpage and ask the client to transfer or redirect a huge amount of money into the criminals' bank account.

7	Harassment and stalking	18,826	This is the use of the Internet to stalk or harass persons, groups, or corporations. These might encompass phony indictment, offence, abuse, insult and smear. It may also include observing, identity theft, threats, harm, damage incitation for sex, or collecting data and information that could be used to intimidate, embarrass, humiliate, discomfit or bully.
8	Obscene publications	6,292	"Pornography that meets the definition of the Obscene Publications Act, thus generally involving some form of physical abuse".
9	Child sexual offences	4,189	"Assault, grooming, indecent communication, coercing a child to witness a sex act. These crimes may be being under-reported".
10	Blackmail	2,028	This is an act of cybercrime that involve false and unwarranted threats to generate, obtain or initiate harm to others unless a demand is fulfilled

Table 1: The ten most common cybercrimes in Great Britain based on current statistics from the National Statistics Office

Cyber security's rising relevance in the financial industry

The results have shown that many institutions, regardless of size and expertise, suffer numerous attempts to break and hack their IT systems. The survey examines the efforts of various financial institutions to avoid and manage cybersecurity threats. Furthermore, nearly all institutions said that, when there was a cyber assault, they had a sort of information security program and software and employed communication officials to answer various questions [7]. To reduce each of these dangers, major expenditures in technology and education are needed. They indicate that it is vital for our customers to work together, be informed of different cyber threats, and maintain privacy in security processes. Cyber-risk measures and control of financial institutions should be as well as any other corporate risk. This is the duty of the teams in the server room and a corporate strategy encompassing all employees. Rising cyber assaults and violations have underlined the necessity in recent years to deal with this form of risk and any other corporate hazards and continually analyze market indicators of changes and dangers.

The impact on cybersecurity of technological progress

Many companies worldwide face the adverse risk of electronic information infringement, making risk management difficult and safe data maintained. The importance of cybersecurity is therefore growing considerably. Due to the significant continuous enhancements in information technology, many new criminal actions have developed that, as they lie beyond the community's moral, social, law, and politics, are difficult to cover by cybercrime rules.

Accordingly, cybercrime is concerned with the electronic environment since it may be described as any unlawful act against computers. Consequently, cybersecurity is necessary to keep secure information. Different scholars have therefore tried to improve the knowledge and relevance of such a notion. The catastrophic violation of 2013, where more than 740 million documents were revealed unlawfully, is one incentive to carry out more studies.

Risk approach for taking the risk out of cybersecurity

The mistakes must be detected, and intervention must be conducted when needed. Firstly, the market failure must be examined and correctly analyzed about social and economic demands within the financial sector. Secondly, it is necessary to investigate the government's involvement in relevant financial instances while considering other practicable interventions, and the outcome, following interventions, should also be predicted. The technical developments and the safety necessary to preserve the current situation are also problems facing the IT department. The necessity for sound management of human resources is also to be taken into consideration. That is one of the major problems of the qualified personnel looking for the appropriate individuals in the right place.

Furthermore, numerous firms do not regard cybersecurity as a concern or danger to the industry [8]. By establishing early planning and designing the steps necessary, they should be involved in early IT initiatives. All technical abilities must be explained to those who are unaware of technical IT issues [9]. Cybersecurity requirements for protecting and critical infrastructure increase at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) (ISACA, 2017). This paradigm is built on the risk approach to cybersecurity removal. The framework gives sector stakeholders the capacity to: understand and utilize the framework to analyze and enhance their cyber resilience; • assess their current and objective cybersecurity postures; • identify gaps in their existing programs for cyber safety risk management;

Nonetheless, to assure the function of cybersecurity, a framework was drawn up to provide five essential tasks needed to safeguard digital assets by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and the European Union Agency for Networking and Information Security (ENISA). The ISACA (2017) noted that these roles synchronize with techniques of incident management, including the following:

- Identify: use the understanding of the organization to reduce the risk for systems, assets, data, and capacity.
- Protection: Design protections to reduce the impact on essential services and infrastructure of probable disasters.
- Detection: implement cybersecurity incident identification operations.
- Response: take the necessary action when a security incident is learned.
- Recover Resilience plan and prompt repair of impaired services.

The political aims must be monitored. Firstly, for the framework of financial regulation and governmental actions, all policy objectives should be clarified. Secondly, all policies adopted within the framework should be based on improvements and possible benefits instead of losses or failures. Thirdly, with priority provided about their systemic risk, the objectives affecting the financial sector's stability need to be adequately prioritized.

Cybersecurity techniques

Several approaches may now be employed to guarantee the security of data of companies. The correct management of devices through the continual deployment of needed updates is one of the key strategies leading to cybersecurity. It is frequently difficult, however, to detect an unauthorized intrusion.

A study performed by professionals has shown only a 51 percent chance of a minor loss of data but a 68 percent chance of a significant data breach. Since a result, these results imply that additional studies on cybersecurity must be carried out as managers are aware of these principles. Information is the company's most important resource; this is why it has to be kept secure, and companies must have secure databases to prevent theft or harm to such information. Damaging information would be damaging to the organization, and that would be the most dangerous thing. For this reason, cybersecurity has been implemented; a company can assess and manage the risk adequately, but occasionally there are loopholes [10]. Organizations now have to pay for this technology, mainly banks and the financial industry, often confronted with cyber-attacks. — More, more sophisticated, and more pervasive cyber-attacks on financial services companies are occurring. Although significant assaults on financial institutions are caused by large-scale denial of service, most headlines, local banks, credit unions, and money transmission companies create. In recent years, tested infringements have been encountered by third-party service providers (e.g., credit card and payment processors).

Cybersecurity's involvement in risk management

Cybersecurity plays an integral part in managing the risk of a company, but senior management tends to focus less on cyber-attacks. Instead, they are waiting for specific cybersecurity rules to be implemented by the government. Scully (2014) therefore said that cyber-attacks influence the success of organizations,

Moreover, CEOs must grasp the cybersecurity problem and idea fully, address this subject routinely with their technical team to identify any dangers to the Business and communicate them between them. Another Vande Putte and Verhelst essay (2014) talks about cybercrime as the notion that it is vital and menacing. They claimed risk management and cyber-crime management are not straightforward and challenging; with the development in technology, these risk effects increase with time. This severe risk is thus essential to recognize because it leads to knowledge loss and a loss of trust. Banks contain many private customers and financial information that needs to be kept secure from the outside. Nearly all companies worldwide now utilize the Internet to conduct their businesses, promote and sell, advertise, explore new markets, buyers, and employees, connect with customers and suppliers and carry out financial operations. The Internet creates massive gates and profits for businesses. It also has hazards, however. Every day, hacking, damage, access to accounts, information, and money was stolen, or business interruptions attack Information Technology Systems [11]. To ensure appropriate attention is

paid to the scale of the hazards involved, the cybersecurity problem requires shifting from information systems professionals to the senior management and board of directors. In creating enormous barriers and firewalls, the usual technique of looking at cybersecurity is no longer appropriate while required. A holistic approach is essential to manage risk cybersecurity - throughout the organization, its network, supplier chains, and the larger ecosystem. However, the external users should know nothing about how the firm secures its information according to cybersecurity risk management.

Role of government and other bodies

Many governments and other entities have recently expressed concerns about this topic, initiating and directing instructions and declaring on the control of cyber assaults. McKendry (2015) says that all financial institutions in the United States are responsible for supervising, using various tools and software, and ensuring high-level awareness of cyber-threats.

V. METHODOLOGY

Quantifiable data were obtained from 26 financial organizations in Bahrain after researching the theoretical portion of cybersecurity in the financial industry. One hundred managers and their workers received an online questionnaire through e-mail. The survey hyperlinks were suggested for employees and colleagues in the same and various banking and financial businesses. The survey was available for four weeks online and downloadable on Google Forms. Data from 35 respondents, who answered the questionnaire, were obtained by conventional banks, Muslim banks, insurance companies, capital markets, and specialized banks. Most were conventional and Islamic banks, with over 90 percent. The questionnaire includes demographics, multiple choices, questions of opinion, and unfinished issues. Data were examined to reveal the proportions of each question explained in the survey. Subsequently, Google Forms were used to gather findings and to evaluate them. A questionnaire was given to 26 financial organizations categorized in the Kingdom of Bahrain for managers and staff to answer preliminary questions. It was classed as traditional banks, Islamic banks, insurance firms, investment banks, capital markets, and specialists [12]. The obtained data were then evaluated to improve the importance of this study and respond to the questions given.

The Study Findings

The data gathering and analysis procedure are described in this part. As seen in the figure, half of the respondents were conventional banks' workers, and the other half were Islamic banks. The demographic selected to conform with the research purpose consists of IT and Accounting workers with cybersecurity tasks.

Figure 1: The types of financial institutions

The second section of the questionnaire examined the sorts of hazards in Bahrain and the frequency of the presence of financial institutions. Figures 2 and 3 show that over 26% derived online identity theft from financial institutions in Bahrain, 23% suffered deliberate harm to computer systems, and 11% faced hacking. This diversity of cyber dangers demonstrates that cybersecurity escalates and evolves, at least every quarter, in the measure that it perturbs the operations of organizations.

Figure 2: Type of malicious activities that have affected the organizations

Figure 3: The likely occurrence of malicious activities

As cybersafety problems grow, the central emphasis of the board of directors of organizations (BOD). Figure 4 demonstrated that cyber-assaults were immediately notified to the board of directors for further action [13]. The interviewees also agreed that the boards expressed great concern about these assaults and attempted to mitigate cyber safety concerns. Figure 5 demonstrates that implementing security policies, enough financing, and security awareness training mandatory are among the most often used approaches for cyber hazard reduction by boards and top management.

Figure 4: Reporting of cybersecurity attacks within the organization

Figure 5 demonstrates that implementing security policies, enough financing, and security awareness training mandatory are among the most often used approaches for cyber hazard reduction by boards and top management.

Figure 5: The ways BOD and executive managers demonstrate to support cybersecurity risk mitigation.

The expertise and abilities of the team of personnel dealing with cyber attempts are a significant component in determining the efficacy of the cybersecurity approach selected [14]. The fourth portion of the questionnaire was therefore aimed at the primary abilities employees need. According to Figure 6, it was evident that it is the absence of technique which is an essential talent that all workers must react to the various cyber assaults that are a significant skill gap that the Business perceives among its employees. The studies also showed that communication is another skill gap lacking in the staff. Otherwise, the company would have problems reacting to complex and even fundamental problems without these critical abilities. Nonetheless, these companies launch numerous programs to acquire the critical abilities needed to make sure different jobs are successful and effective.

Figure 6: The significant skill gaps that an organization sees among its cybersecurity employees

Figure 7 shows how companies build essential technical abilities in different ways. Most businesses appear to favor

different training techniques for their personnel, including on-the-job training, the usage of technical training centers, training providers from third parties, and certificates.

Figure 7: The various technical skills organizations are seeking to develop among their employee's education.

Figure 8 also indicates that most respondents are confident about the capacity of the security staff to detect problems and respond to them, albeit for basic scenarios only. These businesses should thus try to utilize additional techniques to increase the skills and ability of their workers to respond to various degrees of risk.

Figure 8: The extent to which the organization is confident with its employee's abilities and skills

The level of their intricacy and sophistication also grows as cyber-attack tactics improve throughout the years—more than one kind of violations and attack by organizations nowadays. Therefore, the fourth questionnaire examined the variety of cyber assaults that threatened the security of organizations and the extent to which cybersecurity helped to identify these risks. Figure 9 shows that hackers, cybercriminals, and non-malicious insiders are the principal risks to financial institutions' security [15]. On the other hand, hackers exploit 31% of businesses, with social engineering using 17% and malware and insider stealing using 14%. Therefore, the financial institutions said that 75 percent of these risks had been identified by cybersecurity (Figure10). In addition, corporations did not entirely agree about the possibility of cyber assaults by organizations.

Figure 9: The various threats that exploited the organization

Figure 10: The extent to which cybersecurity assists in detecting the various risks

Figure 11 indicates the difference between firms on this issue since 37 percent of respondents feel their organizations are likely to be cyber-attacked, and 31 percent say that cyber-attacks are improbable. The latter hypothesis might be due to progress in cybersecurity and improved talents and competencies.

Figure 11: Expects to experience Cyber-attacks in the future

VI. RESULTS & FINDINGS

The respondents said that banks are vulnerable to three critical threats, internet theft recognized, computer systems purposefully damaged, and hacked. Banks are also regularly subjected to cyber assaults. Some 26% of financial institutions confronted robbery online, while 23% suffered deliberate damage to computer systems, and 11% faced hacker efforts. This range of cyber risks shows the escalation and evolution of cybersecurity, in so much as cybersecurity, interrupts operations at least quarterly. In this questionnaire, the role of the board and other executive directors in removing the dangers of cyber-attacks was examined. The results indicated that the board of directors is promptly informed of the cyber-attacks to take further action [16]. The interviewees also agreed that the Board of Directors is very concerned about the assaults and makes various efforts to mitigate cybersecurity threats. The study demonstrates the most common strategy for reducing cyber-risks by the board of directors, managing security rules, providing adequate money, and demanding safety awareness training. The expertise and abilities of the cyber attempt team constitute a significant component for determining the efficiency of the cybersecurity approach used. In addition, the result has shown that the substantial skill gap in the organization's workers lies in the lack of the necessary technical expertise to which all employees should react. The results also showed that communication is another talent that is lacking for the employees. The company will have trouble addressing complicated or even fundamental challenges without these two key capabilities.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

As cybersecurity problems keep evolving, they are the attention of the boards of directors of financial institutions (BOD). Consequently, several suggestions for banks were offered, including the need to improve cybersecurity and technical abilities for personnel. There is no disputing that companies of financial services are a prominent target for cyber attacks. Most thieves target financial companies simply because the money is there. Despite significant attempts to protect themselves against increasing and more sophisticated assaults, companies in this industry need to remain vigilant. A worldwide and creative strategy is required to address the dangers facing the financial sector successfully. One of the first and most significant measures towards adequate protection should comply with the appropriate legislation.

In the financial sector, cybersecurity plays high importance in guaranteeing its assets are safe, efficient, and dependable. In the increasingly linked and digitized post-COVID world, this is especially true. The numerous cyber dangers they confront must be more aware of business executives in the banking industry. In summary, financial institutions must be proactive in protecting their clients, data, networks, and criminal activities. Financial sector cybersecurity policies should also be designed to enhance cooperation between banks and other

financial institutions. Sharing information about attacks and simulations is fantastic to practice. They may not stop all cyber assaults - they may make a significant difference in preventing and lowering detection and reaction times. They can also prevent attacks and prevent attacks.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The significance of cybersecurity and risks has lately been increasing due to the growing use of technology in the banking industry through the dependency on online banking and e-banking. This has boosted hackers' and criminals' cyber assaults to steal important information and money from financial institutions. Based on an analysis of the crucial findings of this study, it can be stated that three categories of risk are primarily exposed among the many types of harmful actions in Bahrain. These hazards include online identity theft, computer systems purposefully destroying, and hacking. At least once every three months, over half of these financial institutions face similar problems, indicating the increased risk of cyber-attacks. Banks, therefore, notify the board of directors or the auditing sector of the institution of these assaults to prevent such dangers quickly. In addition, the findings gave solutions to the questions raised by the study. In answer to the first question, half of these banks feel confident in their abilities and expertise, although this trust is confined to bare instances.

In reply to the second question, the executive teams of the banking industry promote cybersecurity by applying security policy, providing security and adequate funds for their businesses, and requiring training on security awareness. The third question states that to identify cyber-attacks as a whole, it is essential to have the technical expertise which, as chosen by a majority, may be increased through the necessary training that answers the fourth question [17]. Finally, in response to Question 5, cybersecurity appears to detect 75% of the threats faced by banks. Finally, the results have shown that the fundamental motive of cyber assaults is financial advantages, which offers Bahrain's financial institutions significant risks. Many constraints restrict this study. A key input is that further replies would add value to this study, as the feedback obtained from this questionnaire is significant. Despite the constraints above, the results of this study are essential for banking and financial organizations in Bahrain since they may utilize these data to improve their workers' abilities in the detection of various cyber threats.

Furthermore, these results are of considerable relevance for broadening the understanding and effect on these financial institutions about cybersecurity. Nevertheless, technological measures are a vital part of the practice. Cybersecurity is not only a technical problem, although policy analysts and others can easily forget the technical nuances. In addition, what we know about cybersecurity is typically divided into disciplines and reduces the insights that cross-fertilization provides. Some of these links are illuminated with the primary. Above all, it tries to put two key concepts behind the reader. The problem of

cybersecurity is never once and for all resolved. Although restricted in breadth and durability, solutions to the problem are at least as non-technical as they may be technological in character. Therefore, protecting client assets is a clear justification for the necessity of cybersecurity in banking industry activities. As more individuals become uncashable, internet checkouts and physical credit scanners are used for activities. The PII may be routed to other places in both instances and utilized for nefarious purposes.

This affects not only the client. It also hurts the bank considerably when trying to retrieve the data. When taken hostage, the bank might have to pay the information hundreds of thousands of dollars. Their clients and other financial institutions are losing their confidence.

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